

Removing Casein From Milk

Author: Ishan Gopal

Grade: 12th Grade

August 20, 2025

1 Introduction

This morning, I was scrolling through my instagram reels when I came across an experiment. The person in the reel (I'm not really sure if they were a guy or a girl) mixed vinegar in milk and a white solid precipitated at the bottom of the beaker. After doing a bit more research I found out that it was "Casein" that was being precipitated. Casein is the main protein in cow milk. Well, that was when I decided I wanted to try and do this myself and learn about how this whole process happens, and most importantly, what is the chemistry behind it? I have tried my level best to keep this experiment entry errorless and fact check everything that I have stated, but there might be a possibility that I may have missed a few things or got something wrong. I apologise for that. I am still a highschool student who is in love with chemistry and I'm open to learning about the concepts that I haven't understood well.

2 Materials Used

- One 100ml beaker
- Two 250ml beakers
- An electric hot pot
- 180–200ml of water
- 200ml of milk
- 60ml of chilli vinegar (4% acetic acid)
- A glass stirrer
- A funnel
- Filter paper
- pH paper

3 Procedure

1. First I filled the electric hot pot with 190ml of water and turned on maximum heating. After 3–4 minutes, the water began to bubble which indicated that it started boiling.

Figure 1: Electric hot pot

2. After that, I poured 200ml of milk into a 250ml beaker (The milk was heated previously and then refrigerated for 7 hours. I don't know if that's relevant.)

Figure 2: 200ml milk

3. I then turned the heat down and placed the beaker in the boiling water for 5 minutes.

Figure 3: 200ml of milk in a warm bath

4. While the milk was being heated, I poured in 60ml of the chilli vinegar into a 100ml beaker. The chilli vinegar contained 4% acetic acid.

Figure 4: 60ml of vinegar

5. After 5 minutes when the milk was warm to touch but not too hot, I removed it. The warmness indicated that the milk was around 40–50°C.
6. I then started pouring the vinegar into the warm milk slowly while continuously stirring and measured the pH after every 5–10 seconds. You are supposed to use a dropper but I didn't have one, so I used one hand to slowly pour vinegar into the milk and the other to stir the solution at a constant speed. After 10 seconds or so, white insoluble mass started to form and the solution went from a milky white to a pale yellow color. It looked like the vinegar was turning the liquid milk into a solid, insoluble squishy mass. This precipitate is the casein present in the milk.

Figure 5: Casein precipitated in the milk-vinegar solution

7. To separate the casein from the milk-vinegar solution, I first thought of decantation but soon observed fine casein particles floating in the solution. Hence, I decided to filter it out. I did not have the circular filter paper, only the square ones that you get with the coffee machine so I had to improvise. And I know, it doesn't look the best but it worked just fine!

Figure 6: filtration setup

8. After separating the solution and the precipitate, I had 2 beakers. One with the Casein and the other with the “whey” (pale yellow solution). I also rinsed the casein with water so that I was sure no acetic acid was left. It was also a good idea to filter instead of decanting since the filter paper actually collected some casein.

(extracted casein left in the beaker)

(extracted casein collected in the filter paper)

(Whey solution)

4 Observation

- The Whey solution obtained was measured to be 240ml. This means 20ml of casein was obtained.
- The casein was soft, sticky and I noticed that it was pliable when rinsing it.
- It took 3 minutes for the casein to fully separate.
- The curd had a faint odour of vinegar after rinsing.
- Dried out casein was firm, rubbery and a little flexible.
- The pH of the milk was 6.5 before treatment with vinegar and it became 4.5-4.7 after the treatment with vinegar. This is called the isoelectric point of the casein, I'll explain what this is in the next section. Me, being the smartest tool in the

shed, forgot to take the picture of the pH papers. The following graph shows the readings I got with varying volumes of vinegar.

Figure 7: pH vs vinegar volume

5 Chemistry of Milk

Well, that was how to isolate casein from cow milk, but what about the chemistry behind it? Why did vinegar separate the casein from the milk? Why did the milk have to be warm? What is the meaning of “isoelectric point” I mentioned prior? Well, I’ll answer that question for you! Let’s start from the very beginning.

- **Milk:** Milk is a complex emulsion. It contains water, lactose, and proteins. The main protein of cow milk is casein (about 80%), which is a family of phosphoproteins. This means there are 3 types of casein present and they are, α -, β -, κ -caseins (alpha, beta and kappa).
- **Casein:** Casein is a polypeptide chain with amino acid residues and this includes groups that have charges on them, i.e. carboxylate, amine, etc. Casein in milk exists as micelles, these are colloidal aggregates that get stabilized by the calcium phosphate bridges and the hydrophobic interactions. This is the reason why casein is soluble in milk at its natural pH i.e. 6.5.

Figure 8: Photo of micelles under a microscope

- **Warming the milk:** Heating the milk will cause the weak forces to weaken even further. These weak forces are the van der Waals forces and the hydrogen bonds within the micelles. This makes the casein molecules more accessible to the vinegar.

- **Addition of vinegar to the milk:** Vinegar has acetic acid, a weak organic acid, present in it. Adding 60ml of it into milk will donate H^+ protons. $CH_3COOH \leftrightarrow CH_3COO^- + H^+$. The negatively charged groups of casein get neutralized by these H^+ ions. $-COO^- \rightarrow -COOH$. This reduces the electrostatic repulsion between the casein molecules, causing the micelles to collapse. The overall pH of the solution is reduced to 4.5–4.8, this value is the isoelectric point!
- **Precipitation:** The casein molecules come together via hydrophobic and hydrogen interactions and form an insoluble curd which separates from the whey. A simplified reaction could be represented as:
Milk proteins + $CH_3COOH_{(aq)} \rightarrow$ Casein \downarrow + $Whey_{(aq)}$

6 Disposing

- The whey solution is mostly water so I drained it out the sink.
- Since casein is organic and mostly protein, I composted it in one of my mom's flower pots.
- Beakers, Stirring Rod, Spatula, Funnel were cleaned thoroughly with dish soap and warm water.
- Filter paper, pH paper and my gloves were disposed in the trash after being packed in a plastic bag.